

Contribution to the Valorization of Textile Waste by Slow Pyrolysis

Fernandez-Ferreras J.¹, Pérez-Gandarillas L.¹, Pérez S.², Fernández I.²

¹Department of Chemistry and Process & Resources Engineering, ETSIIyT, Universidad de Cantabria, Avda. de los Castros 46, 39005, Santander, Spain

² Department of Electrical and Energy Engineering, ETSIIyT, Universidad de Cantabria, Avda. de los Castros 46, 39005, Santander, Spain

E-mail contact: josefa.fernandez@unican.es

Keywords: Slow Pyrolysis, Lignocellulosic Textile Waste, Bioenergy and Bioproducts.

1. Introduction

1.1. Textile wastes

The Industrial Revolution introduced technological advancements, leading to faster and more efficient production methods to produce fabrics for clothing, culminating in the establishment of the first textile factories [1]. Natural fibers are those derived from the transformation of raw materials of animal or plant origin and can be turned into threads or cords. Plant fiber is essentially cellulose, with the most commonly used ones being cotton, flax, and esparto. Artificial fibers result from the modification of natural fibers, such as rayon or viscose and lyocell. The textile industry, a key player in the global economy, has historically contributed to environmental threats, including vast water consumption, significant carbon emissions, and the generation of substantial textile waste, producing 92 million tons of textile waste each year [2]. According to the National Institute of Statistics, in 2020, Spain collected 40 thousand tons of textile waste, accounting for 0.17% of the total urban waste collected. Of this amount, 3.1% belongs to Cantabria. Additionally, in the same year, 5% of the total collected waste was incinerated, 28% was disposed of in landfills, and 67% was recycled.

The Law 7/2022 on Waste and Contaminated Soils for a Circular Economy, aims to establish a circular economy through waste legislation. It sets measures to promote reuse and recycling and introduces new separate collections for various types of waste, including textile waste [3]. The ORDER MAM/304/2002 which includes waste valorization and disposal operations and the European List of Waste, categorizes them based on the source generating such waste. Textile waste is classified in Chapter 04 - Waste from the leather, skin, and textile industries [4]. The textile production process consists of obtaining raw materials, spinning, weaving, finishing and manufacturing. The spinning process includes unpacking, carding, combing, first twisting, spinning and finishing.

The transition to a circular economy in the textile industry should involve creating durable garments whose design and style are not dictated by passing trends, utilizing innovative technologies, and promoting second-hand purchases, reuse, retail, recycling and waste reduction to minimize environmental impact through changes in policies and society [5]. Moreover, the textile waste generated in the manufacturing process of natural and artificial fibers is a type of industrial cellulose-rich waste and its valorization for obtaining chemical products and energy can contribute to the goals of the circular economy.

1.2. Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is a process of thermal degradation of a substance in the absence of oxygen, that is, in an inert atmosphere, whereby substances break down by applying heat without combustion reactions occurring [6]. There are three types of pyrolysis: (i) Slow or conventional pyrolysis: Conducted with low heating rates (between 5 and 15°C/min) and temperatures between 300 and 600°C. This method is employed to obtain biochar and a liquid fraction rich in organic acids and other chemical compounds; (ii) Fast pyrolysis: Carried out at temperatures not exceeding 650°C, but with high heating rates. The aim is to obtain a liquid fraction richer in hydrocarbons, intended to be used as biofuel [7]; (iii) Flash pyrolysis: Reaches temperatures of 1000°C and very high heating rates (>1000°C/min), with a high yield of the gaseous and liquid fractions [8]. The gaseous fraction comprises H₂, CO, CO₂, and CH₄ along with more volatile compounds originating from the cracking of organic molecules, in different ratios according to the type of pyrolysis used.

The conversion of textile waste into energy through thermochemical processes is a sustainable recycling option within of the circular economy. This is due to its high cellulose content and calorific value, leading to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and enabling the recovery of carbon and energy [1].

The objective of this study is to explore the technique of slow pyrolysis in the valorisation of different textile wastes of an industrial production process. The research aims to investigate the influence of temperature and waste composition on the obtained fractions (solid, liquid, and gas) while initiating their characterization.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Four kind of textile waste provided by a company from Cantabria were studied in this paper: (i) "*Indigo-dyed Short Fibre Waste*" (ISFW) is the rejection of short yarns resulting from processes like such as scouring, carding, combing, etc. It is a dark blue waste composed of short fibers with low manageability; (ii) "*Card Cabinets Waste*" (CCW) is obtained in the carding stage within the spinning process, where fibers are individually separated, and impurities are removed; (iii) "*Card Waste*" (CW) is a mixture of seeds combined with waste from the cotton separation process in the carding operation. It has an appearance similar to sawdust, as it is a blend of long cotton fibers with remnants of the cotton plant, giving it consistency and making it denser; (iv) "*Cotton Chapón Waste*" (CChW) is also obtained from the carding stage, generated by the action of "chapones," T-shaped metal bars covered with a semi-rigid bent lining. This waste consists of white long cotton fibers and is the lightest of the four. The appearance of all of them can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Appearance of the waste: a) ISFW, b) CCW, c) CW, and d) CChW.

2.2. Pyrolysis Methodology

Conventional (or slow) pyrolysis was performed in a semi-continuous lab scale plant (Figure 2). The plant consists of an "ISUNI" electric oven that can reach temperatures of up to 1000°C, with a PID controller. Inside, a quartz reactor is inserted vertically. Special glass wool was placed for high temperatures acting as a support, and the sample is deposited. The upper and lower parts of the reactor are connected by spherical ground joints lubricated with high vacuum silicone grease. A heating mantle covers the lower elbow to maintain the temperature. The recuperation system consists of three flasks in series for the condensation of volatile liquids, connected using silicone tubes and submerged in cooling baths.

Figure 2 The experimental installation used.

Experiments at a heating rate of 15 °C/min were carried out in triplicate to 6 g of the textile residue in its original size in the vertical fixed-bed quartz reactor in nitrogen flow (300 cm³/min), heated at 300, 400, 500, and 600°C during one hour. The solid and liquid fractions were obtained by weighing and the gaseous fraction by difference.

2.3. Characterization of raw materials and pyrolysis fractions

The pH of the pyrolysis liquid fractions at all the temperatures, measured without dilution, was determined using a CRISON (Barcelona, Spain) pH meter and calibrated solutions of pH 4 and 7 and density was determined by using 5 cm³ volumetric flasks. To determine the higher heating value of raw materials and solid pyrolysis samples, an IKA C5003 Control brand calorimeter was used, equipped with a C5000 controller and a C5001 cooling system.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characterization of raw materials

Table 1 displays the composition of the wastes analysed in this work, provided by the company. The lignocellulosic composition, as well as the ash content was previously described [9-11] and are detailed in Table 2. The most abundant lignocellulosic content is cellulose, as both cotton and linen are natural fibers. Lyocell (also known as Tencel) is an artificial fiber produced by using wood from certified forests that thrive without pesticides, fertilizers, or irrigation. It requires less water for cultivation than cotton, and water is recycled in the manufacturing process.

Table 1 Composition of the production where each waste was obtained.

ISFW	CCW	CW	CChW
12% Cotton 85% Lyocell 1% Linen 1% Synthetic polyester (PES)	70% Lyocell 30% Linen	40% Cotton 30% Lyocell 30% Linen	100% Cotton

Table 2 Lignocellulosic composition of textile wastes.

	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	Lignin (%)	Ash (%)
Lyocell	97.5	-	0	0.9
Cotton	96	2.4	0	1.3
Linen	83.3	11.3	2.3	1.8

3.2. Pyrolysis results

Figure 3 compare average values the solid, liquid, and gaseous fractions obtained by pyrolysis of the four textile residues studied, conducted at each temperature.

Figure 3 Evolution of the pyrolysis fractions with temperature for the four textile residues: a) Solid fraction; b) Liquid fraction; c) Gaseous fraction.

For the solid fraction, a decrease is observed for all the wastes as the temperature increases. In the case of the liquid fraction, there is an initial increase up to 500°C, followed by a slight decrease, except for the CW residue, which exhibits an increase from 500 to 600°C. The maximum value is obtained in the case of CChW at 500°C. Regarding the gaseous fraction, it represents the minority at all temperatures, with a tendency to increase as the temperature rises. In general, the CChW residue produces the lowest percentage of gases.

According to the composition of the residues shown in Tables 1 and 2, the CChW residue, composed of 100% cotton and with a composition of cellulose (96%) and hemicellulose (2.4%) (Table 2), achieves the highest pyrolysis liquid value, reaching 60.3% at 500°C and 55.9% at 600°C. CCW and CW residues, containing a higher linen content (30%), exhibit the highest percentages of solid fraction at 400 and 500°C, reaching values of 51.6% (CW at 300°C). The higher content of linen in lignin (which decomposes at higher temperatures) and ashes also explain this result. To achieve the highest liquid content with an important solid fraction, a pyrolysis temperature of 500°C is recommended for most of the textile wastes, except in CW where 600°C seems more appropriate.

3.3. Characterization of the reaction products

Liquid Fractions. The pH of the liquid fractions at all temperatures is presented in Table 3. The pH values found are acidic in all cases, ranging between 1.36 and 3.64. These values correspond to some of the compounds commonly found in the liquid fraction of pyrolysis, such as various carboxylic acids, along with alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, and furans, as reported in previous studies [12]. In other studies of cellulose-based materials, similar pH values have been found. For instance, in the pyrolysis of rice husk, a pH of 3.2 is obtained; for wood, a pH of 2.5, and in the pyrolysis of paper waste, a pH of 1.5 [13]. It can also be observed that the liquids resulting from the pyrolysis of residues with higher cellulose content and less lignin have a more acidic pH (ISFW and CChW). Regarding the density values shown in Table 4, they are higher than that of water in all cases but close to it, ranging between 1.024 (CCW at 300°C) and 1.161 (CChW at 500°C). These values, along with the low pH values of these fractions, indicate that the liquid fraction is an aqueous solution with presence of organic acids that contributes to both acidity and a density higher than that of water (formic acid, 1,2183 g/cm³, acetic acid, 1,049 g/cm³).

Table 3 pH of the liquid fractions obtained at the different pyrolysis temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	pH			
	ISFW	CCW	CW	CChW
300	1.36	2.92	3.38	2.20
400	1.87	3.19	3.64	2.47
500	1.61	2.45	3.46	2.10
600	3.00	2.89	3.56	1.68

The liquid fraction of the CW residue exhibits very similar densities to those found for the CCW, as both residues contain 30% linen. The CChW residue, composed of 100% cotton, has the liquid with the highest densities (1.059 to 1.161 g/cm³), followed by the liquid obtained from the pyrolysis of ISFW, where cellulose is predominant but also contains 1% linen and 1% PES. As a result, they will have a higher proportion of acids [14], which aligns with the lower pH of this fraction. Therefore, a higher cellulose content produces a more acidic and dense pyrolysis liquid compared to compositions containing lignin.

Table 4 Density of the liquid fractions obtained at the different pyrolysis temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	Density (g/cm ³)			
	ISFW	CCW	CW	CChW
300	1.045	1.024	1.028	1.059
400	1.034	1.026	1.032	1.134
500	1.046	1.034	1.033	1.161
600	1.050	1.047	1.033	1.114

Solid Fractions. Table 5 displays the results of the higher heating value of the original samples and the solid fractions obtained through pyrolysis at 300°C, 400°C, 500°C, and 600°C. Initial heating value of the textile residues are similar (15.46 to 16.57 kJ/kg), with slightly higher values for ISFW and CChW, with the highest cellulose content. The heating value increases substantially after pyrolysis but varies little with increasing temperature. The values for the CCW and CW residues are similar since both contain 30% linen. The ISFW residue has lower ash content as it is mainly composed of cotton and lyocell, similar to the CChW residue, which is composed of 100% cotton, presenting higher values than the previous ones. CChW provides the highest heating values, surpassing 33 MJ/kg, comparable to bituminous coal.

Table 5 Higher heating values of raw materials and pyrolysis solid fractions.

Temperature (°C)	High Heating Values (MJ / kg)			
	ISFW	CCW	CW	CChW
Raw material	16.57	16.08	15.46	16.53
300	29.00	23.37	24.63	28.96
400	28.99	26.81	20.93	31.89
500	28.70	27.96	23.93	33.48
600	28.70	24.61	22.91	33.01

4. Conclusions

The slow pyrolysis of four textile residues have been studied. Results have shown that the solid fraction decreases with increasing temperature, while the gaseous fraction increases. However, the liquid fraction increases reaching its maximum at 500°C, becoming the most significant fraction from 400°C onwards. The pyrolysis of the CChW residue yields a higher amount of liquid fraction at any temperature, while the solid fraction is greater for the CCW and CW residues. All studied wastes show significant potential for the production in the liquid fraction of carboxylic acids such as formic and acetic acids, along with other organic compounds. This is more pronounced in the case of CChW and ISFW, related to the highest cellulose content and lowest ash and lignin content. Moreover, the solid pyrolysis fraction demonstrates high calorific value (up to 33.48 MJ kg⁻¹ in CChW), justifying its potential use as a fuel. A pyrolysis temperature of 500°C is considered the most favourable for the studied textile residues to obtain chemicals from the liquid fraction and bituminous coal-like solid fraction fuels. In conclusion, the study underscores the potential of slow pyrolysis in addressing some environmental challenges posed by textile waste, aligning with the principles of the circular economy.

5. References

- [1] Athanasopoulos, P., & Zabaniotou, A. (2022). Post-consumer textile thermochemical recycling to fuels and biocarbon: A critical review. *Science of the Total Environment*, 834, 155387.
- [2] Centobelli, P., Abbate, S., Nadeem, S. P., & Garza-Reyes, J. A. (2022). Slowing the fast fashion industry: An all-round perspective. *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 38 (100684).
- [3] España. (2022). Ley 7/2022, de 8 de abril, de residuos y suelos contaminados para una economía circular. *Boletín Oficial Del Estado*, 9 de abril de 2022, 85, pp. 1–137.
- [4] España. (2002). Orden MAM/304/2002, de 8 de febrero por la que se publican las operaciones de valorización y eliminación de residuos y la lista europea de residuos. *Boletín Oficial Del Estado*, 19 de febrero de 2002, 43, 6494-6515.
- [5] Núñez-Tabales, J. M., Del Amor-Collado, E., & Rey-Carmona, F. J. (2021). Economía circular en la industria de la moda: Pilares básicos del modelo. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 27, 162–176.
- [6] Bridgwater, T. (2018). Challenges and opportunities in fast pyrolysis of biomass: Part I. *Johnson Matthey Technology Review*, 62 (1), 118–130.
- [7] Tessini, C., Segura, C., & Berg, A. (2013). Pirólisis rápida de biomasa. In *Bioenergía & Biorrefinería- Canade-Açúcar & Espécies Florestais*, 459-482.
- [8] Amutio, M., Lopez, G., Aguado, R., Artetxe, M., Bilbao, J., & Olazar, M., (2011). Effect of vacuum on lignocellulosic biomass flash pyrolysis in a conical spouted bed reactor. *Energy and Fuels*, 25(9), 3950–3960.
- [9] Silva, C. G., Benaducci, D., & Frollini, E. (2012). Lyocell and cotton fibers as reinforcements for a thermoset polymer. *BioResources*, 7(1), 78–98.
- [10] Chen, F., Sawada, D., Hummel, M., Sixta, H., & Budtova, T. (2020). Swelling and dissolution kinetics of natural and man-made cellulose fibers in solvent power tuned ionic liquid. *Cellulose*, 27(13), 7399-7415.
- [11] Reed, A. R., & Williams, P. T. (2004). Thermal processing of biomass natural fibre wastes by pyrolysis. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 28(2), 131-145.
- [12] Yang, H., Yan, R., Chen, H., Lee, D. H., Liang, D. T., & Zheng, C. (2006). Mechanism of palm oil waste pyrolysis in a packed bed. *Energy and Fuels*, 20(3), 1321-1328.
- [13] Hoang, A. T., Ong, H. C., Fattah, I. M. R., Chong, C. T., Cheng, C. K., Sakthivel, R., & Ok, Y. S. (2021). Progress on the lignocellulosic biomass pyrolysis for biofuel production toward environmental sustainability. *Fuel Processing Technology*, 223 (106997).
- [14] Salas, Y., Arroyo, C., Mercedes, C., & Lazo, A. B. (2008). Obtención y caracterización fisicoquímica y funcional de las fibras dietéticas del níspero común (*Mespilus germanica*). *Rev Soc Quím Perú*, 74(4), 269-281.

Acknowledgements - This research was funded by Solvay, under projects 3399 and 3824, EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions—RISE, grant number 101007733 (CELISE project) and Government of Cantabria “Bridge Projects 2023” (PID2022-138142OB-I00).